

Application of the spectral element method based on the hierarchical Poincaré-Steklov scheme to fluid modelling of low-temperature plasmas

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Abstract

We examine the application of a spectral element method based on the hierarchical Poincaré-Steklov (HPS) scheme to one-dimensional fluid modeling of low-temperature plasma discharges. The HPS scheme is a direct solver for second-order boundary value problems that employs a hierarchical domain decomposition procedure. Its structure is well suited for adaptive mesh refinement, enabling efficient resolution of critical regions in the spatiotemporal evolution of plasma discharges. In this work, the HPS scheme is applied to the numerical solution of the hydrodynamic equations describing direct-current and radio-frequency argon discharges between parallel-plate electrodes. Adaptive mesh refinement is employed based on criteria involving the local spectral properties of the solution. The results demonstrate that adaptive mesh refinement within the HPS scheme effectively resolves regions exhibiting steep gradients in the solution during the simulation.

1 Introduction

Numerical modelling of low-temperature plasmas is an important tool for analyzing plasma discharge properties and understanding the underlying physical processes. Among the various numerical approaches, fluid modelling is widely used for low-temperature plasma simulations at elevated pressures, where the mean free path of plasma species becomes much smaller than the characteristic length scales of the discharge. Under these conditions, the plasma can be described by continuum hydrodynamic equations formulated in terms of macroscopic quantities. In many cases,

one-dimensional fluid models are sufficient to capture the essential features of plasma behavior and provide valuable insight into the underlying discharge physics [1–5].

In general, the numerical treatment of one-dimensional plasma fluid models results in a coupled system of second-order boundary value problems that must be solved simultaneously. Spatial discretization is commonly performed using either the finite-difference method or the finite-element method. To accurately capture steep gradients and localized features, mesh refinement is often employed in critical regions of the computational domain. In most applications, this refinement is performed statically, with the computational mesh remaining fixed throughout the simulation. However, low-temperature plasma discharges often exhibit complex spatiotemporal structures that evolve throughout the simulation. Consequently, adaptive mesh refinement may be of particular importance, as it allows the computational mesh to adjust dynamically to changing solution requirements.

The incorporation of adaptive mesh refinement into conventional finite-difference and finite-element solvers is often hindered by the limited flexibility of the underlying data structures employed during the numerical solution process. It is therefore of interest to explore alternative solution strategies that are better suited to the implementation of adaptive mesh refinement.

One such approach is the finite-element method based on the hierarchical Poincaré–Steklov (HPS) scheme [6]. The HPS scheme solves second-order boundary value problems through a hierarchical domain decomposition procedure based on the recursive construction and merging of Dirichlet-to-Neumann operators. In the HPS scheme, the computational mesh is organized as a binary tree of intervals, providing a flexible hierarchical framework that is particularly well suited for adaptive mesh refinement. Moreover, the HPS scheme typically employs high-order local discretizations, which facilitate the construction of accurate solution interpolation procedures during adaptive mesh refinement.

In this paper, we demonstrate the applicability of the HPS scheme to one-dimensional fluid modelling of low-temperature plasma discharges and investigate its potential for adaptive mesh refinement. For this purpose, we consider a reference argon discharge problem that has recently served as a benchmark for the intercomparison of various plasma simulation codes [7]. The model description is presented in Section 2. A brief overview of the numerical method employed is provided in Section 3. The numerical experiments are presented in Section 4. Concluding remarks are given in Section 5.

2 Model description

2.1 Governing equations

We consider an argon plasma consisting of ground-state atoms (Ar), electrons (e), positive ions (Ar^+), and metastable atoms (Ar^*). The metastable atoms are represented by a single lumped excited state combining the two argon metastable levels $\text{Ar}[1s_5]$ and $\text{Ar}[1s_3]$ (Paschen notation). The number densities of the plasma species

are governed by the continuity equations

$$\frac{\partial n_\alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \Gamma_\alpha}{\partial x} = S_\alpha, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha = e, \text{Ar}^+, \text{Ar}^*$, and Γ_α and S_α denote the particle flux and chemical source term of species α , respectively. The number density of argon atoms is assumed to remain constant at the value corresponding to the considered gas pressure.

The flux of species α is described within the drift–diffusion approximation as

$$\Gamma_\alpha = q_\alpha \mu_\alpha E n_\alpha - D_\alpha \frac{\partial n_\alpha}{\partial x}, \quad (2)$$

where E is the electric field, q_α is the particle charge, μ_α is the particle mobility, and D_α is the particle diffusion coefficient.

The electron mobility, μ_e , and electron diffusion coefficient, D_e , were treated as functions of the mean electron energy and were obtained by solving the spatially homogeneous Boltzmann equation, as described in [1]. The ion mobility μ_{Ar^+} was taken from [8] as a function of the electric field. The ion diffusion coefficient was determined using the Einstein relation. The diffusion coefficient of metastable atoms was set to $n_{\text{Ar}} D_{\text{Ar}^*} = 1.7 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [9].

Table 1 Chemical reaction scheme used in the model. The rate coefficients are defined as in [1]. The rate coefficients of the electron-impact processes are obtained by solving the spatially homogeneous Boltzmann equation (BE).

No.	Reaction	Rate coefficient
R1	$e + \text{Ar} \rightarrow e + \text{Ar}^*$	BE
R2	$e + \text{Ar} \rightarrow 2e + \text{Ar}^+$	BE
R3	$e + \text{Ar}^* \rightarrow 2e + \text{Ar}^+$	BE
R4	$\text{Ar}^* + \text{Ar}^* \rightarrow e + \text{Ar} + \text{Ar}^+$	$8.1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
R5	$\text{Ar}^* \rightarrow \text{Ar}$	10^6 s^{-1}

The details of the chemical reaction scheme used in the model are presented in Table 1. The reaction rate coefficients were calculated as described in [1]. The rate coefficients of the electron-impact processes were treated as functions of the electron mean energy and were obtained by solving the spatially homogeneous Boltzmann equation. The chemical source terms S_α in Eq. (1) were calculated from the reaction scheme listed in Table 1 using the standard definitions of reaction rates and stoichiometric coefficients.

The electron energy density, w_e , is obtained by solving the electron energy equation

$$\frac{\partial w_e}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q_e}{\partial x} = -q_e E \Gamma_e - n_e P_{\text{el}} - P_{\text{in}} \quad (3)$$

where Q_e is the electron energy flux, P_{el} is the energy loss per electron due to elastic collisions of electrons with the background gas, and P_{in} is the energy loss due to

inelastic collisions. The electron energy density is defined as $w_e = n_e \varepsilon_e$, where ε_e is the mean electron energy.

The energy loss due to elastic collisions, P_e , was computed by solving the spatially homogeneous Boltzmann equation [1]. The energy loss due to inelastic collisions, P_{in} , was calculated according to the reaction scheme presented in Table 1 as described in detail in [1].

The electron energy flux is determined using the drift–diffusion approximation with simplified transport coefficients:

$$Q_e = -\frac{5}{3}\mu_e E w_e - \frac{5}{3}D_e \frac{\partial w_e}{\partial x}. \quad (4)$$

Equations (1) and (3) are coupled with the Poisson equation for the electric potential:

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{dx^2} = -\frac{e}{\varepsilon_0} (n_{Ar^+} - n_e), \quad (5)$$

where φ is the electric potential, e is the elementary charge, and ε_0 is the vacuum permittivity. Accordingly, the electric field is given by $E = -d\varphi/dx$.

2.2 Boundary conditions

Equations (1), (3), and (5) are solved on the interval $x \in [0, d]$, where d denotes the electrode gap. The equations are supplemented with appropriate boundary conditions, as discussed below.

The continuity equation for the metastable atoms is subject to the boundary condition

$$\Gamma_{Ar^*} \nu = \frac{1}{4} v_{Ar^*}^{th} n_{Ar^*}, \quad (6)$$

where $\nu = -1$ at $x = 0$ and $\nu = 1$ at $x = d$ denote the outward unit normal to the boundary, and $v_{Ar^*}^{th}$ is the thermal velocity of the metastable atoms. This velocity is defined as $v_{Ar^*}^{th} = \sqrt{8k_B T_g / \pi m_{Ar}}$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T_g is the gas temperature, and m_{Ar} is the mass of an argon atom.

The continuity equation for the argon ions is subject to the boundary condition

$$\Gamma_{Ar^+} \nu = \left(\max(v_{Ar^+}^d \nu, 0) + \frac{1}{4} v_{Ar^+}^{th} \right) n_{Ar^+}, \quad (7)$$

where $v_{Ar^+}^d$ and $v_{Ar^+}^{th}$ are the ion drift and thermal velocities, respectively. The ion drift velocity is given by $v_{Ar^+}^d = e\mu_{Ar^+} E$ and the ion thermal velocity is given by $v_{Ar^+}^{th} = \sqrt{8k_B T_g / \pi m_{Ar^+}}$, with m_{Ar^+} being the ion mass.

The electron continuity equation is subject to the boundary condition

$$\Gamma_e \nu = \left(\max(v_e^d \nu, 0) + \frac{1}{4} v_e^{th} \right) n_e - \gamma \max(\Gamma_{Ar^+} \nu, 0) \quad (8)$$

where γ is the secondary electron emission coefficient, and v_e^d and v_e^{th} are the electron drift and thermal velocities, respectively. The electron drift velocity is given by $v_e^d =$

$-e\mu_e E$ and the electron thermal velocity is given by $v_e^{\text{th}} = \sqrt{8k_B T_e / \pi m_e}$, with m_e being the electron mass and $T_e = (2/3k_B)\varepsilon_e$ being the electron temperature.

The electron energy balance equation is subject to the boundary condition

$$Q_e \nu = \left(\max\left(\frac{5}{3}v_e^{\text{d}}\nu, 0\right) + \frac{1}{3}v_e^{\text{th}} \right) w_e - \gamma\varepsilon_\gamma \max(\Gamma_{\text{Ar}^+}\nu, 0), \quad (9)$$

where ε_γ is the mean energy of secondary electrons.

The Poisson equation is subject to the boundary condition

$$\varphi = \begin{cases} U(t), & x = 0, \\ 0, & x = d, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $U(t)$ is the voltage applied to the powered electrode.

3 Numerical method

The governing equations described in Section 2.1, together with the boundary conditions specified in Section 2.2, were solved numerically using a spectral element method based on the hierarchical Poincaré–Steklov (HPS) scheme. To this end, the continuity equations (1) and the electron energy balance equation (3) were first discretized in time using the second-order backward differentiation formula [10]. This temporal discretization reduces the governing equations to a sequence of boundary value problems for the species densities, electron energy density, and electric potential. The resulting problems, subject to the boundary conditions described in Section 2.2, were then solved using the spectral element solver described in [6].

Within the spectral element solver, the computational interval is represented by a binary tree of subintervals. Starting from the root interval, additional nodes are generated through recursive bisection of their parent intervals, resulting in a hierarchical decomposition of the computational domain. The resolution of the hierarchical discretization is characterized by the refinement level, which corresponds to the depth of a node within the binary tree. On the leaf nodes of the binary tree, the governing equations are discretized using a spectral Galerkin method based on Gauss–Lobatto nodes. For all numerical experiments reported in this work, six Gauss–Lobatto nodes were employed on each leaf interval.

The binary-tree discretization was constructed adaptively. In all simulations, adaptive mesh refinement was used to refine or coarsen the hierarchical decomposition as required by the evolving solution. The adaptive mesh refinement strategy was based on indicators derived from the local spectral properties of the ion density and electron mean energy. The refinement indicators were defined according to the following procedure.

For each leaf interval, the solution was expanded in a Legendre polynomial basis, yielding the expansion coefficients c_i , $i = 0, \dots, 5$. The smoothness indicator was

computed from the Legendre expansion coefficients as

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sum_{i=2}^5 c_i^2}{\sum_{i=0}^5 c_i^2}. \quad (11)$$

The characteristic smoothness indicator was computed as the maximum of the smoothness indicators associated with the ion density and electron mean energy.

Based on the characteristic smoothness indicator, adaptive mesh refinement and coarsening were performed according to the following criteria. A node was refined whenever the characteristic smoothness indicator exceeded 10^{-3} , provided that its refinement level did not exceed 8. Coarsening was applied only to nodes whose child nodes were leaf nodes. The two child leaf nodes were merged into their parent node whenever the characteristic smoothness indicators on both leaf nodes were below 10^{-3} and the refinement level of the parent node was greater than 3. Adaptive mesh refinement and coarsening were carried out every 50 steps of the time integration scheme.

4 Numerical experiments

The numerical experiments in this work were performed at a gas pressure of 133 Pa and an electrode gap of 1 cm. The secondary electron emission coefficient and the mean energy of secondary electrons were set to 0.06 and 5 eV, respectively, following the values reported by [1]. The initial particle densities were assumed to be uniformly distributed throughout the computational domain. The initial electron and ion densities were set to 10^{12} m^{-3} . The initial metastable atom density was assumed to be zero. The mean electron energy was assumed to be uniformly distributed and set to 3 eV throughout the computational domain. A constant time step of 0.02 ns was used throughout the computations.

4.1 DC discharge

The first test case considered a direct-current (DC) discharge. In this case, the potential at the powered electrode was fixed at -250 V , following the conditions considered in [1]. The simulation was run up to $15 \mu\text{s}$.

Figure 1 shows the spatial distributions of the plasma species number densities at selected time instants during the discharge development. The corresponding spatial distributions of the mean electron energy are presented in Figure 2.

To illustrate the effect of adaptive mesh refinement, Figure 3 presents the spatial distributions of the ion number density at two selected time instants, together with the corresponding element-size distributions. The figure demonstrates that the mesh is refined in regions with high solution gradients while remaining coarse in regions where the solution varies smoothly. For the considered example, the effect of adaptive mesh refinement is most pronounced between 1 and $5 \mu\text{s}$, when strong gradients in the ion number density develop. In this case, mesh adaptation is driven by the smoothness factor of the ion number density. As shown in Figure 3, at $t = 1 \mu\text{s}$ the mesh is refined in a region where the ion number density exhibits a strong spatial gradient.

Fig. 1 Spatial distributions of plasma species number densities at selected time instants in a DC discharge.

Fig. 2 Spatial distributions of the mean electron energy at selected time instants in a DC discharge.

This example demonstrates the capability of the adaptive mesh refinement algorithm to dynamically adjust the computational mesh and maintain an optimal number of elements throughout the simulation.

Fig. 3 Spatial distributions of the ion number density and the corresponding element size at two selected time instants in a DC discharge.

4.2 RF discharge

The second test case considered a radio-frequency discharge operating at 13.56 MHz. The powered electrode was driven by a sinusoidal voltage with an amplitude of 250 V. The simulation was run until a periodic steady state was reached.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of plasma species number densities at different stages of the discharge period. The distributions are characterized by smooth spatial variations and the absence of steep gradients. In this case, adaptive mesh refinement is driven by the spatial variations of the electron mean energy, shown in Figure 5. The mean electron energy reveals steep gradients near the electrodes. Accordingly, the adaptive mesh refinement concentrates smaller elements in these regions to accurately resolve the sharp variations. This behavior is illustrated in Figure 6, which shows the mean electron energy together with the local element size at different times during the discharge period. This example demonstrates the ability of the adaptive mesh refinement algorithm used in the present work to adjust the number of elements based on the local solution properties.

5 Conclusion

The spectral element method based on the hierarchical Poincaré–Steklov (HPS) scheme has been applied to one-dimensional fluid modelling of low-temperature plasma discharges. Its performance was assessed using benchmark argon direct-current and

Fig. 4 Number densities of plasma species at different stages of the discharge period (T).

Fig. 5 Spatial distribution of the electron mean energy at different times during the discharge period (T).

radio-frequency discharge problems. The focus was placed on the application of adaptive mesh refinement to accurately capture spatiotemporal variations in the discharge structure. Adaptive mesh refinement was implemented by exploiting the hierarchical structure of the HPS scheme. Local spectral properties of the ion density and mean electron energy were employed as refinement indicators to guide the mesh adaptation

Fig. 6 Spatial distribution of the electron mean energy (blue line) and element size (green line) at different times during the discharge period (T)

process. The numerical experiments showed that the HPS scheme provides an effective framework for the simulation of one-dimensional fluid models of low-temperature plasmas. The applied adaptive mesh refinement algorithm was able to identify and resolve critical regions of the solution by dynamically adjusting the number of elements in the computational mesh. These results indicate that the HPS framework provides a promising basis for efficient and accurate adaptive simulations of low-temperature plasma discharges.

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